

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D6.2 INITIAL COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, STANDARDISATION AND EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	Fifth Generation
6G	Sixth Generation
SNS	Smart Networks and Services Industry
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CORD	Central Office Re-architected as a Datacenter
CLAIRE	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe
DIDs	Decentralised Identities
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union

FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
FL	Federated Learning
H2020	Horizon 2020
HW	Hardware
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NDM	Nokia Data Marketplace
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
ODL	OpenDaylight
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSF	OpenStack Foundation
OSM	Open Source MANO (Management and Orchestration)

OTA	Over the Air
Ph.D.	Doctor of Philosophy
PU	Public
RATS	Remote Attestation Procedures
RIS	Reconfigurable Radio Systems
SA	Security for AI
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
VM	Virtual Machine
WP	Work Package
XMSS	Extended Merkle Signature Scheme
ZKP	Zero-knowledge Proofs

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document presents the results of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project during the first 18 months, outlining strategies and activities to effectively communicate results, share knowledge, and maximize commercial potential.

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project has achieved good progress in its dissemination and communication efforts. Specifically, the project has published 4 peer-reviewed journal articles and 11 conference papers. Consortium members have participated in various international conferences and workshops, featuring presentations, posters, and panel discussions. The SECURENET Summit on Security and Privacy in Future Mobile Networks 2024, organized by the project, successfully attracted over 200 attendees. The project website has been a key tool for dissemination, attracting 7,780 unique visitors. Social media engagement has managed to achieve 788 followers and on LinkedIn, X and Youtube. The project has also released two newsletters and issued three press releases, effectively reaching a wide audience through various media channels.

To enhance stakeholder engagement and outreach, the project has initiated targeted campaigns such as "Meet the Partners" and "Women in STEM," showcasing consortium partners and promoting diversity. The establishment of a Zenodo community page has contributed 16 publications, with 478 downloads, supporting the project's open access and data sharing initiatives.

In terms of standardization, the CONFIDENTIAL6G project has actively participated in ETSI, ISO, and NIST standardization efforts, including workshops and collaborative sessions. The project has developed three key exploitable results—Confidential Toolkit, Confidential Computing, and Confidential Networking—each with detailed exploitation strategies tailored to ensure sustainability and impact.

The project has also focused on various communication and dissemination metrics, including 521 contact points through email campaigns, distribution of 200 flyers, 200 brochures, 2 posters, and 2 rollups, totalling 404 printed materials. Additionally, 3 slide decks have been shared, and 1 webinar/workshop has been conducted with significant participation. Although some targets like developer community contributions and multimedia materials are still in progress, the project has made significant traction.

Overall, the CONFIDENTIAL6G project has successfully implemented its initial plans for dissemination, communication, and exploitation. These efforts have resulted in high visibility and engagement within the research and industrial communities, effective use of digital platforms, strong contributions to standardization, and development of key exploitable results. This sets a solid foundation for ongoing and future activities, contributing to the project's long-term goals of enhancing cybersecurity and privacy in 6G networks.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE

The deliverable D6.2, titled "Initial Communication, Dissemination, Standardisation, and Exploitation Activities (M18)," presents a detailed overview of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project's outreach and impact initiatives during the first 18 months. It summarises how the project has communicated its findings and technologies, sharing its scientific and technological achievements with a broader audience.

In the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, Work Package 6 (WP6) plays an important role in the project's success by engaging with diverse stakeholders and existing ecosystems from the very beginning. This deliverable presents the activities related to ecosystem building, standardisation, intellectual property rights (IPR) management, and the initial steps towards commercial exploitation. It highlights the strategies and actions taken to establish a strong foundation for the project's communication and dissemination efforts, ensuring that the project's advancements and results reach relevant audiences through various channels such as conferences, workshops, journals, and standardisation forums.

By summarising these initial activities, D6.2 provides insights into the project's progress and lays the groundwork for ongoing and future efforts to maximise the impact and sustainability of CONFIDENTIAL6G.

1.2 DOCUMENT ORGANISATION

The document is organised into several sections, each addressing specific aspects of the project's communication and dissemination strategy:

- Section 1 - Introduction: this section provides an overview of the document's scope.
- Section 2 - Dissemination and Communication Actions and Performance: This section details the dissemination and communication activities executed, including the use of established dissemination tools and channels, as well as participative dissemination efforts by consortium partners. It highlights events participated/organized, scientific publications, and outreach activities.

- Section 3 - Exploitation: This section focuses on the exploitation strategy of the project, identifying key exploitable results and outlining business models and exploitation plans for each partner.
- Section 4 - IPR Knowledge Management: This section discusses the management of intellectual property rights, ensuring clear guidelines for identifying, owning, and granting access to research outcomes.
- Section 5 - Dissemination and Communication KPIs and Project Monitoring: This section presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) and the monitoring approach for dissemination, communication, and impact creation activities.
- Section 6 - Conclusion: This section summarises the overall communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy, emphasizing the importance of continuous updates and alignment with project progress.

2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIONS AND PERFORMANCE

The majority of our ongoing outreach and dissemination efforts have been executed according to plan through two primary communication streams. The first stream involves established dissemination tools and channels managed by the Project, with content primarily authored, compiled, edited, and mediated by ZEN, the lead of WP6. The second stream consists of activities carried out by individual or collaborating partners. These include scientific and technical publications, co-organisation and participation in events such as conferences, congresses, and fairs, as well as leveraging their own thematic and expertise networks for targeted and informal communication.

2.1 PARTICIPATIVE DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

2.1.1 EVENTS PARTICIPATED/ORGANIZED, AND RELATED SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Involvement of CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium members in various national and international conferences, congresses, summits, fairs, workshops, and other events, whether they attract large audiences or are focused on experts, plays a crucial role in our communication, dissemination, and outreach efforts. This involvement also facilitates direct engagement with stakeholders, as detailed in Chapter 2.3.

During the project's initial phase, our participating partners have primarily concentrated on:

- Raising awareness about the Project and its aims, goals, and values.
- Sharing preliminary results at conferences and symposiums.

At a few significant events, such as conferences and tradeshow, our consortium partners have taken on roles in:

- Organising the events.
- Engaging more deeply and directly with attendees.
- Collecting valuable feedback and ideas from the audience.

As the Project progresses and more results are generated, we plan to enhance this interaction in the second phase. According to our plan, the Project has organised its own event SECURENET Summit on Security and Privacy in Future Mobile Networks 2024, Dublin. We regularly update our list of potential events for participation or attendance based on the Project's focus and stage, adapting as opportunities and circumstances arise.

Table 1 highlights the participation of CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium partners in major international events during the reported period, showcasing their contributions and including relevant live on-site photographs.

Table 1 List of dissemination and communication activities

Event	Date and place	Photo/ Link	Type of contribution
ETSI Conference Research	06-08.02 2023, Sophia Antipolis, France		Presentation and poster
European Convention Blockchain	15- 17.02.2023. Barcelona, Spain		Booth
International Conference on Advanced Research in Computing 2023	23- 24.02.2023 , Online	Blockchain for 5G and Beyond Networks, Link	Speaker slot
3rd webinar of the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) on the Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services an	23.02.2023. Online	Project presentation (Slides Video)	Presentation

AI for Good, Enabling intrusion detection in 5G networks via novel datasets	02.03.2023 , Online	Link	Panel
CrossFyre 23 (affiliated to Eurocrypt 23)	23.04.2023. Lyon, France	Link	Event participation
Human Factor in Digital Transformation	27 April 2023, Graz, Austria	Link	Speaker, Invited Talk
6G Global Summit 2023	03- 04.05.2023 . Bahrain	<i>Panellist for Session 4: Securing the Future: Cyber Security in the 6G Era</i>	Panel
Tomorrow Conference	12- 14.05.2023. Belgrade Serbia		Event participation
2023 EuCNC & 6G Summit	06- 09.06.2023. Gothenburg, Sweden	Video feature (Project Coordinator)	Featured video
IFIP Networking / TC6 meeting	12.06.2023. Barcelona, Spain	Link	Meeting participation
2nd CITEA Digital Cyprus Conference 2023	22.06.2023. Cyprus	Link	Speaker
Monero Konferenco	23- 26.06.2023 Praha	Link	Speaker

BLOCKCHANCE 2023	June 28-30 2023, Hamburg, Germany	Link	Attendee, on- event project consultation and communication
Nordic Congress of Mathematicians NCM29	July 6 2023, Aalborg, Denmark	/	Speaker
The Confidential Computing Summit 2023	June 29 2023, San Francisco	Link	Speaker
Cyber Ireland National Conference 2023	27 September 2023, Galway, Ireland	Link	Attendee

<p>The SECURENET 2023 Summit</p>	<p>11 September 2023, Dublin, Ireland</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker</p>
<p>Corunna Innovate Summit</p>	<p>26-27 October, La Coruña, Spain</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker, Invited Talk</p>
<p>Fuse5G</p>	<p>19 January, Utrecht, Netherlands</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker</p>
<p>6Gsec Common Path and Cardinal Points "6Gsec CP2"</p>	<p>23 January 2024, Paris, France</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker, Panellist for Session 2: Secure AI for Secure 6G and Session 3: Crypto-based technologies application in 6G</p>

<p>Itinerant Seminars Cryptography</p>	<p>2 February 2024, Barcelona, Spain</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker</p>
<p>CODE-KOLLOQUIUM</p>	<p>21 February 2024, Munich, Germany</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Invited Talk</p>
<p>Public Key Cryptography (PKC 24)</p>	<p>16 April 2024, Sydney, Australia</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Speaker, Talk of Accepted paper</p>
<p>OpenInfra Computing Group Edge Working</p>	<p>15 January 2024</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Presentation in Openstack Edge Computing Working Group</p>

<p>Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2024</p>	<p>26-29 February 2024</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Communication of the project results</p>
<p>The 2nd SECURENET Summit on Security and Privacy in Future Mobile Networks 2024</p>	<p>21 May 2024, Dublin, Ireland</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Organiser</p>
<p>EuCNC & 6G Summit 2024 conference</p>	<p>3-6 June 2024</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Booth with posters and demos</p>
<p>EuROCRYPT conference</p>	<p>26-30 May 2024</p>	<p>Link</p>	<p>Paper Presentation</p>

Security in Times of Surveillance Workshop	31 May 2024	Link	Invited Talk
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The estimated number of attendees directly engaged through these event participations reaches thousands.

The audience mainly consists of experts and researchers from the scientific/technological research communities and industries, including:

- Telecommunications (with a focus on 6G technology)
- Computer science
- Cybersecurity
- Information Technology (IT)
- Software development
- Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)
- Quantum computing and cryptography

Representatives from the social sciences and humanities (SSH), including ethics experts, are also part of the audience.

Additionally, officials and members from EU initiatives and associations have been present.

- Public authorities and policymakers, such as:
 - Ministries
 - National government representatives
 - Local, municipal, or regional authorities
- Media representatives, including:
 - National and local TV
 - Newspapers and other print media publishers

Table 2 compiles the scientific and technological peer-reviewed publications authored by CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium partners during the initial phase of the Project. These publications, including those published in journals, as well as those featured at the events specified in the aforementioned table, with updated publication links and release versions as of June 2024.

Table 2 Published papers and articles by the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium partners

No	Authors	Title	Title of Journal or Conference	Link	Type
1.	Thien Huynh-The, Thippa Reddy Gadekallu , Weizheng Wang , Gokul Yenduri , Pasika Ranaweera , Quoc-Viet Pham , Daniel Benevides da Costa , Madhusanka Liyanage	"Blockchain for the metaverse: A Review"	Future Generation Computer Systems, Elsevier	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167739X23000493	Journal
2.	Chamitha De Alwis; Pawani Porambage; Kapal Dev; Thippa Reddy Gadekallu; Madhusanka Liyanage	"A Survey on Network Slicing Security: Attacks, Challenges, Solutions and Research Directions"	IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials Volume: 26 Issue: 1	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10242032	Journal
3.	Pramitha Fernando; Keshawa Dadallage; Tharindu Gamage; Chathura Seneviratne; An Braeken; Arjuna Madanayake; Madhusanka Liyanage	"Distributed -Proof-of-Sense: Blockchain Consensus Mechanisms for Detecting Spectrum Access Violations of the Radio"	IEEE Transactions on Cognitive Communications and Networking, Volume: 9 Issue: 5	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10171207	Journal

		Spectrum"			
4.	Rashmi Ratnayake, Madhusanka Liyanaage, Liam Murphy	"Trust Management and Bad Data Reduction in Internet of Vehicles Using Blockchain and AI"	2023 IEEE 97th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2023- Spring)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10200207	Conference
5.	Charithri Yapa, Chamitha De Alwis, Uditha L. Wijewardhana, Madhusanka Liyanaage	"Utilization of a Blockchain- based Reputation Management System for Energy Trading in Smart Grid 2.0"	2023 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10361893	Conference
6.	Pramitha Fernando, An Braeken, Madhusanka Liyanaage	"Breaking Chains, Empowering IoT: A Comparative Study of Holochain and Blockchain"	2023 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10361851	Conference
7.	Lakshan Pathiraja, Isuru Lakshan, Kavini Kushani, Chamara Sandeepa, Tharindu D. Gamage, Thilina Weerasinghe, Madhusanka Liyanaage	"Privacy- preserved Collaborative Federated Learning Platform for Industrial Internet of Things" -	2023 IEEE Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10361886	Conference

8.	Nisita Weerasinghe, Tharaka Hewa, Anshumaan Kalla, Mika Ylianttila, Madhusanka Liyanage	"Blockchain enabled Private 5G Networks: A Primer"	2023 Fifth International Conference on Blockchain Computing and Applications (BCCA)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10338873	Conference
9.	Thiwanka Silva, Madhushika Bamunuge, Dilusha Dissanayake, Chatura Seneviratne, Tharindu Gamage, Madhusanka Liyanage	"Proof of Equation: A Novel Consensus Algorithm for Dynamic Spectrum Access"	2023 IEEE AFRICON	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10293543	Conference
10.	Awaneesh Kumar Yadav, An Braeken, Mika Ylianttila, Madhusanka Liyanage	"A Blockchain based Authentication Protocol for Metaverse Environments using a Zero Knowledge Proof"	2023 IEEE International Conference on Metaverse Computing, Networking and Applications (MetaCom)	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10271834	Conference
11.	Thomas Attema, Serge Fehr, Michael Klooß, Nicolas Resch	"The Fiat-Shamir Transformation of $(\Gamma_1, \dots, \Gamma_\mu)$ -Special-Sound Interactive Proofs"	Cryptology ePrint Archive	https://eprint.iacr.org/2023/1945.pdf	Journal
12.	Claudia Bartoli, Ignacio Cascudo	"On Sigma-Protocols and (packed) Black-Box Secret	27th IACR International Conference on Practice and Theory of	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-	Conference

		Sharing Schemes"	Public-Key Cryptography	57722-2_14	
13.	Ignacio Cascudo, Bernardo David	"Publicly Verifiable Secret Sharing over Class Groups and Applications to DKG and YOSO"	Advances in Cryptology – EUROCRYPT 2024 43rd Annual International Conference on the Theory and Applications of Cryptographic Techniques	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-58740-5_8	Conference
14.	Charithri Yapa, Chamitha de Alwis, Uditha Wijewardhana, Madhusanka Liyanage, Janaka Ekanayake	"Utilization of a blockchainized reputation management service for performance enhancement of Smart Grid 2.0 applications"	Journal of Industrial Information Integration Volume 39, May 2024, 100580	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2452414X24000244	Journal
15.	Sven Schäge	"New Limits of Provable Security and the Case of ElGamal PKE"	Advances in Cryptology – EUROCRYPT 2024 43rd Annual International Conference on the Theory and Applications of Cryptographic Techniques	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-58737-5_10	Conference

These publications are featured in top-referred impactful journals and proceedings series covering a range of fields including blockchain technology, cybersecurity, cryptography, machine learning, AI, network security, and Smart Grid applications.

This ensures that the disseminated progress and knowledge generated through the CONFIDENTIAL6G Project meet high standards and maximize their impact and outreach.

The relevant links are provided in the Repository Link column on the publications page of the CONFIDENTIAL6G Project [website](#). This greatly enhances the Project's Open Research efforts, supported by its established dissemination and communication tools and channels, as detailed in the following section.

2.2 DISSEMINATION THROUGH PROJECT TOOLS AND CHANNELS

2.2.1 CONFIDENTIAL6G WEBSITE

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project acknowledges the significance of its website as a crucial platform for disseminating project updates and engaging with stakeholders. This report presents an overview of the website's activity, emphasising updates and new sections introduced since its launch on 03/12/2023, on the <https://confidential6g.eu> domain.

Figure 1 CONFIDENTIAL6G WEBSITE Mockup

To ensure the website remains informative and valuable for visitors, its content is regularly updated and enhanced. New sections and content have been added to provide the most current information and resources, with the site continuously evolving through relevant feature updates and additions. The most notable enhancements include:

Regular News and Updates:

A dedicated section for news and updates has been implemented to keep visitors informed about the project's latest developments. This section is frequently refreshed with new content, featuring 29 posts during the reported period.

Added Deliverables Subsection:

Within the Documents section, a new subsection has been created to list all project deliverables. This includes links to download the (currently four approved by the EC) public deliverables, ensuring project outputs are easily accessible to visitors. Additionally, 14 entries have been posted in the Publications subsection.

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	WP no	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)	Download
D1.1	CONFIDENTIAL6G Project Management Handbook and Risk Management Plan	WP1	1 - WINGS	R - Document_report	SEN - Sensitive	3	Download PDF
D1.2	Quality Assurance	WP1	1 - WINGS	R - Document_report	SEN - Sensitive	3	Download PDF
D1.3	Data Management Plan (v1)	WP1	1 - WINGS	DMP - Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	6	Download PDF
D1.4	Project review report (v1)	WP1	1 - WINGS	R - Document_report	SEN - Sensitive	18	
D1.5	Data Management Plan (v2)	WP1	1 - WINGS	DMP - Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	18	
D1.6	Data Management Plan (v3)	WP1	1 - WINGS	DMP - Data Management Plan	SEN - Sensitive	36	
D1.7	Project review report (v2)	WP1	1 - WINGS	R - Document_report	SEN - Sensitive	36	
D2.1	Post-quantum Analysis Report	WP2	5 - TUE	R - Document_report	PU - Public	12	Download PDF
D2.2	Confidential Networking Toolkit	WP2	9 - TNO	R - Document_report	PU - Public	24	
D2.3	Confidential Computation Toolkit	WP2	5 - TUE	R - Document_report	PU - Public	30	
D2.4	Blockchain Toolkit	WP2	12 - UCD	R - Document_report	PU - Public	30	
D3.1	Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Computing in 6G	WP3	2 - NNF	R - Document_report	PU - Public	12	Download PDF
D3.2	Hardware Platform Support for Confidential Computing	WP3	6 - UVC	R - Document_report	PU - Public	24	
D3.3	Confidential multi-party AI/ML	WP3	9 - TNO	R - Document_report	PU - Public	30	
D3.4	Embedded Confidential Computing	WP3	8 - VTT	R - Document_report	PU - Public	30	
D4.1	Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking in 6G	WP4	3 - NOK	R - Document_report	PU - Public	12	Download PDF
D4.2	Secure Decentralized Data Sharing	WP4	2 - NNF	R - Document_report	PU - Public	18	
D4.3	Confidential Orchestration	WP4	8 - VTT	R - Document_report	PU - Public	30	
D4.4	Federated AI/ML	WP4	12 - UCD	R - Document_report	PU - Public	36	
D5.1	Pilot requirements definition and integration report	WP5	4 - TID	R - Document_report	PU - Public	24	
D5.2	Pilot execution report	WP5	4 - TID	R - Document_report	PU - Public	56	
D6.1	Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities	WP6	7 - ZEN	R - Document_report	PU - Public	6	Download PDF
D6.2	Initial communication, dissemination, standardisation and exploitation activities	WP6	7 - ZEN	R - Document_report	PU - Public	18	
D6.3	Report on communication, dissemination, standardisation and exploitation activities	WP6	3 - NOK	R - Document_report	SEN - Sensitive	36	

Figure 2 CONFIDENTIAL6G website deliverables section

Newsletter Archive:

An archive for previous project newsletters has been incorporated into the website. This feature allows visitors to access the (currently three) previous editions, enabling them to stay informed about past project activities.

Throughout the reporting period, the website has consistently attracted visitors. Detailed metrics indicate that 7780 unique visitors have accessed the site, resulting in a total of 16048 visits (within the generally “good” visits performance indicator level range of 2000 to 4000, as defined in the D6.1 plan), reflecting sustained interest in project updates and information.

Table 3 CONFIDENTIAL6G Website statistics

Number of unique visitors	Total number of visits
7,780	16,048

Figure 3 CONFIDENTIAL6G Newsletter Archive section

The CONFIDENTIAL6G website acts as a vital platform for project communication. By consistently updating content and introducing new sections, the site effectively provides essential information to stakeholders. Ongoing efforts will focus on further improving the website to serve visitors better and enhance its overall impact.

2.2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS

CONFIDENTIAL6G is active on social media, especially on X and LinkedIn as these platforms are effective for connecting with technology communities.

LinkedIn is the main platform for interacting with professionals, industry experts, and stakeholders in technology and innovation where the project shares updates, achievements, and relevant content to build connections and initiate discussions within the professional community.

X is used to deliver real-time updates, news, and announcements related to the CONFIDENTIAL6G project enabling quick and efficient communication with a wide range of people including researchers, practitioners, etc.

The social media accounts for confidential6g are:

- X: https://twitter.com/C6G_eu
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/c6g-project/>
- Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@CONFIDENTIAL6G>

Table 4 provides the breakdown of communication KPIs and outcomes over these channels.

Table 4 Breakdown of communication KPIs and outcomes over social media channels

Channel	Total Followers	Number of posts	Impressions
	284	55	13,263
	29	44	614
	6	1	10

2.2.3 NEWSLETTERS

We have released two newsletters over the past period each well-designed to deliver project news and updates to our audience.

Figure 4 CONFIDENTIAL6G Newsletters

By distributing these newsletters, we keep our subscribed stakeholders informed and engaged with the project's progress. The design elements also improve readability and effectiveness, helping to capture the attention of our readers. We will continue to share valuable insights and updates through our newsletters to maintain strong connections with our audience.

2.2.4 PRINTED MATERIALS

Our efforts have been directed towards creating and developing essential promotional materials for our project.

The main ambition of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project is to enable secure and privacy-preserving computation via novel, modern cryptographic techniques and operations across the cloud-edge continuum that will be necessary in 6G.

Prerequisites for implementation of privacy preservation and security of data in these heterogeneous environments and different contexts is robust modern cryptographic techniques, tools and libraries.

This is why it is essential to focus the research on these security enablers as well, especially with the awareness of danger that can be posed by near-future quantum computers and their capabilities to break the contemporary encryptions.

CONFIDENTIAL6G will research post-quantum cryptography (PQC) in order to create tools, libraries, SDKs and other artefacts needed for future 6G technologies

- Domain #1: Confidential Computing enablers: Lattice-based cryptography for Fully Homomorphic Encryption, Secure Multi-party Computation, TEE attestation handling, collaborative AI/ML.
- Domain #2: Confidential Communication enablers: PQC TLS and other protocols/IO, Blockchain-based data exchange, Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKPs), Confidential Smart Contracts, Decentralised Identifiers (DIDs) and Verifiable Credentials (VCs), and a new concept of Anonymous Credentials (AC).
- Domain #3: Confidential Edge and IoT enablers: embedded PHE, PQC for constrained devices, large-scale networks of connected devices involved in federated learning and cryptography necessary to support this.

Figure 5 CONFIDENTIAL6G Rollup

At recent events like the SecureNET 2024 in Dublin and EUCNC 2024, we presented a roll-up banner. Additionally, we have prepared brochures, flyers, notebooks, and pens for future dissemination. These materials are designed to reflect our project's visual identity, featuring a unified colour palette. They feature

the EU flag and funding statement aligning with guidelines set by the European Commission. This approach ensures consistent acknowledgment of the support received from the EU and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) across various communication platforms and interactions. The materials feature 6GSNS logo too since the project receives the support from 6GSNS which is involved in building a collaboration environment for European and global actors preparing for 6G smart networks and services.

Figure 6 CONFIDENTIAL6G Brochure

Figure 7 CONFIDENTIAL6G Flyer

Figure 8 CONFIDENTIAL6G Notebook and Pen

These materials align with our project's visual identity, maintaining a consistent colour scheme and prominently displaying the EU flag and funding statement as well as the 6GSNS logo in accordance with European Commission guidelines.

2.2.5 PRESS RELEASES

The IMDEA Software Institute, Spain issued three press releases in March 2023 and they are accessible via the following links:

- 1 <https://cso.computerworld.es/nuevas-tecnologias/confidential6g-el-proyecto-europeo-que-blinda-la-seguridad-de-la-conectividad-del-manana>
- 2 <https://web.archive.org/web/20230313085322/https://www.lavanguardia.com/vida/20230310/8815162/imdea-software-trabaja-incrementar-seguridad-conectividad-6g.html>
- 3 <https://www.madrimasd.org/blogs/Tecnologiasdelainformacionparaelmundodelmanana/2023/03/08/imdea-software-participa-en-el-proyecto-europeo-confidential6g-para-garantizar-la-fiabilidad-de-herramientas-de-ia-emergentes-y-dispositivos-iot/>

These announced IMDEA's participation in the European project CONFIDENTIAL6G, which aims to enhance the security and reliability of 6G networks, essential for AI tools and IoT devices. The institute stressed the importance of the project in addressing increased security challenges posed by the heterogeneity and mobility of numerous connected devices, through the development of secure computing tools, post-quantum cryptography, and blockchain technologies. With a budget exceeding 5.2 million euros, primarily funded by the European Digital Horizon program, the project brings together 13 entities from 9 countries and is coordinated by Wings ICT Solutions.

2.2.6 INTERVIEWS

The project has planned a series of interviews about various important scientific and technological development areas. These interviews will cover topics related to WP2, WP3 and WP4 as well as the use cases providing details about the technical aspects, objectives, challenges and achievements.

2.2.7 CONFIDENTIAL6G VIDEO

Various clips from key project events have been recorded (with some already been published over social media) and they will be combined into the Project's presentational video.

Efforts are underway to produce and compile an additional supplementary material, with a primary focus on the advancement of demonstrator use cases and the

challenges they address. Upon gathering over 1:30 minutes of content, we will proceed to create the comprehensive presentation video.

2.2.8 NON-SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Confidential partners have consistently authored, edited, and published non-scientific pieces aimed at the general public, primarily in the form of online articles and blog posts. These have been disseminated across the various Project channels mentioned above. A summary of the most notable publications is provided in Table 5.

Table 5 Summary of non-scientific publications oriented to the broad public

Post Title/Subject	Partner Author(s)	Type	Dissemination Channel(s)
CONFIDENTIAL6G Kick-off Meeting	ALL	Blog	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G at ETSI Workshop 2023	NOK,UCD, ZEN	Blog	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G on The European Blockchain Convention	ZEN	Blog	Website
Empowering Women in STEM – Join the C6G Campaign	ZEN	Article	Website LinkedIn
Confidential6g.eu Officially Releases Website to the Public	ZEN	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Project Showcase: Claudia Bartoli Duncan at CrossFyre 23	IMDEA	Article	Website
Fabian Schmid Presents on Privacy by Design at Values by Design Workshop	TUG	Article	Website

CONFIDENTIAL6G at 6G Global Summit 2023	UCD	Article	Website
Zentrix Lab's Presence at TMRW Conference: Connecting with the Blockchain Community	ZEN	Article	Website
CONFIDENTIAL6G project was presented at the Monero Konferenco	FAU	Article	Website LinkedIn
Zentrix Lab Introduces CONFIDENTIAL6G at BLOCKCHANCE 2023	ZEN	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Gains Visibility at Nordic Congress of Mathematicians NCM29	IMDEA	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G at was presented at the IFIP Networking 2023 Conference (NETWORKING 2023) and CITEA Digital Cyprus Conference 2023	TELEFONICA	Blog	Website LinkedIn
Dusan Borovcanin Presents CONFIDENTIAL6G Project at Confidential Computing Summit 2023	UVC	Blog	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Project Update!	ALL	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Introduced at 1st Summit on Security and Privacy in Future Mobile Networks (SECURENET) 2023	UCD	Article	Website LinkedIn

CONFIDENTIAL6G 3rd Plenary Meeting	ALL	Blog	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G at CINC23: Building a Safer Digital Future	UCD	Article	Website LinkedIn
Thomas Attema from TNO Speaks at Fuse5G in Utrecht	TNO	Article	Website
Madhusanka Liyanage from UCD, CONFIDENTIAL6G Partner, Shares Insights at 6Gsec CP ² Event	UCD	Article	Website
Claudia Bartoli from IMDEA Software Institute Speaks at Itinerant Cryptography Seminars in Barcelona	IMDEA	Article	Website
UCD Presents TRUST-SPEC: Advancing Wireless Communication	UCD	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Project Partner Prof. Schröder Presents at CODE-Kolloquium	FAU	Article	Website
2nd Summit on Security and Privacy in Future Mobile Networks (SECURENET) 2024	UCD	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G at EuCNC 2024 Summit	WINGS, UVC, ABSTRACT MACHINES	Article	Website LinkedIn
SECURENET 2024 Summit: Advancing Mobile Network Security	ALL	Blog	Website

CONFIDENTIAL6G at 2024 EuCNC & 6G Summit: Showcasing Innovations and Engaging the Community	WINGS, UVC, ABSTRACT MACHINES	Article	Website LinkedIn
CONFIDENTIAL6G Project Meeting	ALL	Post	LinkedIn

2.2.9 CAMPAIGNS

2.2.9.1 MEET THE PARTNERS

CONFIDENTIAL6G project has developed a targeted campaign to showcase the consortium partner organisations and their corresponding teams. This campaign leverages rich audiovisual content, including videos, live streams, and animations. An example for one partner is provided in the figures below, with similar presentations created for the other partners.

- Link to the LinkedIn meet the Partners Campaign Announcement: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/c6g-project_confidential6g-confidential6g-partners-activity-7041054123844075521-eeenb?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- Link to the X Meet the Partners Campaign Announcement: https://x.com/C6G_eu/status/1635292225117757442
- Link to the Meet the Partner Campaign on LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/c6g-project_confidential6g-integrated-intelligent-activity-7051187939820601346-rMsw?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- Link to the Meet the Partner Campaign on X: https://x.com/C6G_eu/status/1645423484808380418

D6.2 Initial Communication, Dissemination, Standardisation and Exploitation Activities

Figure 9 Meet the Partners - Campaign Announcement

Figure 10 Meet the Partners - Social Media Campaign Template WINGS

Figure 11 Meet the Partners - Social Media Campaign Template

3.1.1.1 2.2.9.2 WOMEN IN STEM

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project has also launched a thematic campaign to highlight and celebrate women in STEM fields within the consortium partner teams, including those in leadership roles. This initiative aims to increase visibility of their achievements and foster collaboration, diversity, and inclusion in STEM, thereby helping to close the gender gap. The campaign features interviews, podcasts, presentations, and other materials produced by various partners and disseminated through the project's social media channels.

This initiative also aims to engage prospective students and youth, particularly the next generation of women in STEM, as well as targeted stakeholder communities within academia, industry, and partially regulatory and governmental sectors. These efforts complement other external stakeholder engagement actions detailed in Chapter 2.3 below.

Figure 12 Women in STEM - Campaign Announcement

Figure 13 Women in STEM - Social Media Campaign Template

[- Women In STEM - Annette Shajan](#)

2.3 STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT, NETWORKING, SYNERGIES AND STANDARDISATION

2.3.1 SYNERGISTIC ENGAGEMENT

The Advisory Board or focus group for the CONFIDENTIAL6G project has been formed, resulting from internal analysis and consultations within the consortium as set out in D6.1, consisting of four representative external expert members selected from main targeted stakeholder groups: IoT, Privacy, 6G and Cloud, Cybersecurity, Standardisation.

These members were chosen based on their strong technical expertise and experience in EU projects, proactivity/initiative, and other desired criteria stated in D6.1 Section 2.3. Table 6 provides details on the chosen focus group members:

Table 6 CONFIDENTIAL6G Focus Group / Advisory Board composition

Name	Organization	Stakeholder Category
Antonio Kung	Dialog	CyberSecurity
Professor Tarik Taleb	University Bochum	IoT
Professor Maryline Laurent	Telecom SudParis	Telco
David Boswarthick	ETSI	Standardisation

The focus group members will provide valuable insights and feedback on the project's progress, submitting detailed reports. Their contributions will be essential in guiding the project toward success.

2.3.2 ACADEMIA, SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY, AND INDUSTRY ENGAGEMENT

The CONFIDENTIAL6G project follows Horizon Europe's open access policy, ensuring that scientific information is accessible and free for end-users while remaining reusable. Horizon Europe stresses the importance of open access to peer-reviewed publications

and curated datasets which aligns with this project's goals of accessibility and transparency. The scientific information appears in various forms as outlined in Section 2.1 above. This includes peer-reviewed articles, pre-print articles, and conference papers. In the next phase, this will expand to include patents, books, and research data. The research data will encompass different data types including curated datasets, but also the raw data, and associated publications and source code associated with how this data was generated, processed, and analysed.

Our commitment to open research goes beyond simply sharing information. It involves active and intensive engagement with targeted researchers and industry experts. This engagement involves using and experimenting with various types of resources including data, research works, and code. Bringing together diverse expertise and resources in a collaborative setting promotes innovation and speeds up the research progress. Zenodo Repository for Project Materials and Open Data

As part of our dedication to open access and research, the CONFIDENTIAL6G project has launched a community page on the Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/confidential6g-project>). This platform serves as a central hub for sharing Open Access materials produced by the project, such as deliverables, publications, and datasets. Aligning with Horizon Europe's Open Research Data Pilot, we ensure that datasets essential for validating publication results are accessible in the Zenodo repository, promoting data accessibility and reuse. While currently hosting a limited selection of planned data, the community is gaining momentum, evidenced by rising visitor and download numbers. Our initial focus has been on sharing generated publications, as detailed in Section 2.1. Moving forward, the Zenodo community will expand to include additional datasets and supporting materials, utilising its increasing engagement to foster more intensive interaction with stakeholders.

Table 7 Zenodo publication statistics

Number of publications on Zenodo	Total views	Total downloads
16	123	478

2.3.3 NETWORKING, CLUSTERING, AND SYNERGIES WITH OTHER PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

Our project is actively involved in creating a network with three other key initiatives focusing on security and telecommunications

- The selected projects, funded by Horizon Europe programme, include:
: SNS JU ELASTIC, HE HARPOCRATES and HE TITAN projects

CONFIDENTIAL6G participates in SNS JU Cluster, enhancing the collaborative efforts and driving innovation within the telecommunication sector.

The purpose of these memberships is to drive innovation and strengthen our network's visibility within the industry. By engaging with these initiatives, we aim to share knowledge, leverage expertise, and contribute to advancements in security and telecommunications.

-

European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU)

CONFIDENTIAL6G, a part of the European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), stands to gain numerous advantages in terms of communication and dissemination of project news and results. SNS JU, a Public-Private Partnership, aims to promote industrial leadership in 5G and 6G networks and services within Europe. By actively engaging with SNS JU, CONFIDENTIAL6G will leverage its social media presence, collaborate with other 6G projects, and tap into the wider ecosystem to amplify its impact and foster technological advancements.

By participating in SNS JU meetings and leveraging their social media channels, CONFIDENTIAL6G can gain increased visibility and recognition among the European and international 6G community. SNS JU brings together diverse stakeholders, providing CONFIDENTIAL6G with valuable networking opportunities to connect with other projects and organisations working on 6G technologies. CONFIDENTIAL6G can tap into the collective expertise, knowledge, and resources available within the SNS JU ecosystem, including technical reports, research findings, and best practices related to 6G networks and services.

Active engagement with SNS JU enables CONFIDENTIAL6G to establish collaborations and partnerships with other projects, industry, and research institutions, fostering joint initiatives and potential future collaborations. Furthermore, participation in SNS JU activities allows CONFIDENTIAL6G to

contribute to the development of standards, guidelines, and policy recommendations in the 6G domain, positioning the project as an influential player and shaping the future of 6G networks and services. By leveraging these benefits, CONFIDENTIAL6G can effectively promote its project, expand its ecosystem, and maximise its impact within the 6G landscape, contributing to Europe's technological sovereignty and the digital transformation of society and the economy.

A summary of activities already performed in the scope of SNS is provided below:

- Input to SNS Call assessment questionnaire Stream B - Strand D, August 2022
- Input to SNS Call assessment questionnaire, October 2022
- Contribution to the SNS Annual Journal 2023 prepared by SNS OPS, February 2023
- Participation at the ETSI/EC/6G-IA workshop on SNS projects Standardisation plans, 6-8 February 2023, ETSI HQs, Sophia-Antipolis, France
- Presentation of project at the 3rd webinar of the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) on the Stream B1 & B4 projects addressing: Architecture & Secure Services and Security, 23 February 2023
- Participation to Preparatory SNS Steering Board meetings (online) on 13 March 2023 and 12 May 2023
- Input for SNS JU Phase 1 - Projects Questionnaire, May 2023
- Participation to “Passing the Torch event: 5G-PPP to SNS JU” (online), 25 May 2023
- Project video feature recorded at the 2023 EuCNC & 6G Summit, 6-9 June 2023, Gothenburg, Sweden
- Participation with the Booth and demos at 2024 EuCNC & 6G Summit, 3-6th June 2023, Antwerp, Belgium

2.4 STANDARDISATION

Standardisation plays a crucial role in facilitating the broader acceptance of new technologies among diverse stakeholders. However, the standardisation process is

typically a long process, often extending well beyond the duration of individual research and innovation projects.

CONFIDENTIAL6G has been active in the standardization by participating in development new signature schemes, working groups and events. More specifically, partners of CONFIDENTIAL6G have been active in the standardization and analysis of cryptographic building blocks and protocols in IETF, ISO, and NIST. The current concrete results can be summarised as follow:

- TUE's PQ signature scheme SPHINCS+ will be standardized by NIST and TUE delivered comments on the draft versions.
- TUE's KEM Classic McEliece is a candidate in the ongoing round 4 of the NIST competition
- TUE is editor and co-editor of an ISO standard draft on the pre-quantum signature system Ed25519 and the post-quantum systems Classic McEliece, Frodo, and Kyber/ML-KEM
- Workshop with other projects at the ETSI Security Conference 2023, in ETSI premises in Sophia Antipolis, France. The project is presented, and Standardisation plans discussed.

2.4.1 ACTION PLAN

ETSI, as a European Standards Organization (ESO), provides an open, inclusive, and collaborative environment for its 900+ member organisations, drawn from over 60 countries and five continents. With its special role in Europe, ETSI supports regulations and legislation through the creation of Harmonized European Standards, which are recognized as European Standards (ENs). Accordingly, CONFIDENTIAL6G will facilitate the next edition of the ETSI conference in October 2024 and explore other potential areas for standardisation in the 6G industry, relaying on the collaboration and cooperation in the development of the 6G infrastructure to meet the needs of both industry and society. Accordingly, the action plan can be summarized as follows:

- Presentation of the proposal for the ETSI Security Conference 2024: "CONFIDENTIAL6G: Confidential Computing and Privacy-preserving Technologies for 6G", will be presented in ETSI premises in Sophia Antipolis, France, 14-17 October 2024.

- The PQ signature scheme SPHINCS+, developed by TUE, is set to be standardized by NIST. TUE has already provided feedback on the draft versions.
- TUE's Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) Classic McEliece remains a strong candidate in the current round 4 of the NIST competition.
- TUE continues its role as editor and co-editor for an ISO standard draft that covers both pre-quantum and post-quantum signature systems, including Ed25519, Classic McEliece, Frodo, and Kyber/ML-KEM.

3 EXPLOITATION

3.1 BUSINESS MODEL

CONFIDENTIAL6G recognises three main exploitation models for the project results: 1) the commercial exploitation model, which implies the paid provision of the project results to the end users, complying with a licensing scheme which will be defined at a later stage, 2) the research exploitation model, which implies the use of the research know-how acquired in future research activities, and 3) the technological exploitation model, which implies the use of the technological know-how gained for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them. CONFIDENTIAL6G will use a custom designed template in order to characterise key exploitable results, both on individual partner level and joint level. Different versions of the template will be created depending on the exploitation model which will be used.

Table 8 Business Model Canvas

Indicative Business Model Canvas				
Key partners	Key activities	Value proposition	Customer relationship	Customer segment
Telco providers, Cloud providers, Critical ICT infrastructures; academia, ICT vendors and asset providers; open-source communities;	Design and development of cybersecurity risk management and services; business model development for new services; maintenance and integration.	Framework for enhancing cyber security, privacy and data protection of complex ICT infrastructures; Secure and robust cloud	Long term support and future upgrades; training support; community support; dedicated assistance.	Telco providers; Cloud providers, Professionals; Public authorities; executives and managers of service providers; third

<p>standardization organizations; investors; early adopters and promoters.</p>	<p>Key resources</p> <p>Scientific and research results from the project activities; successful validation of use cases.</p>	<p>and edge infrastructure, network layer resilience to attacks; data and privacy and advanced federated processing operations,</p>	<p>Channels</p> <p>Website, social media; demonstration & dissemination activities; standardization , open source; clustering; fairs and events.</p>	<p>party developers; CERTs/CSIRTs; cybersecurity educational providers and training firms; cybersecurity researchers.</p>
<p>Cost structure</p> <p>R&D costs; infrastructure costs (i.e. platform hosting); data centre operations; integration costs; marketing costs & ads; customer support.</p>		<p>Revenue streams</p> <p>Open source versus closed system services (licensing); tools on demand (API); direct platform sales; after-sales service; engineering services; consulting services; development contracts</p>		

CONFIDENTIAL6G identifies main target groups' categories that may be interested in the commercialisation of the project results: Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Academia.

The **actual exploitation plan** (Figure 15) has been elaborated and will be frequently updated, aiming at maximising the exploitation levels of the project, from the involved target groups. It includes the following **four phases**:

1. **Discovery Phase:** Gathering market insights and defining business requirements while shaping the project's value proposition.
2. **Strategy Phase:** Developing the business model and analysing the competitive landscape to define the project's positioning and market entry strategy.

- 3. Partnership Phase:** Creating a comprehensive business plan and securing partner buy-in to ensure collaboration and alignment with the project's goals.
- 4. Validation and Commercialization Phase:** Validating the requirements, finalizing the go-to-market strategy, and establishing a long-term sustainable framework for potential commercialization of the project's offerings.

Figure 14 Exploitation plan

3.2 KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULTS

In CONFIDENTIAL6G we have already identified preliminary key exploitable outcomes. As the project progresses, the detailed plan for utilising these outcomes will be developed gradually based on the intentions of our various partners. This plan will encompass the regular definition of exploitable outcomes, including technical results, methodologies, and knowledge generated by the project. These key exploitable outcomes will be evaluated based on their current stage of development, potential impact, differentiation from existing concepts or products, and other relevant factors. Ultimately, at the project's conclusion, we will produce a comprehensive roadmap for exploiting these outcomes (D6.3).

Here is a summary of the initial collective key exploitable outcomes, which will undergo further refinement and development during the project:

- Valuable Outcome #1: Confidential Toolkit
- Valuable Outcome #2: Confidential Computing
- Valuable Outcome #3: Confidential Networking

- Proof of concept for Use Case 1: Implementation of predictive maintenance for an airline consortium using a blockchain-based data sharing platform and federated AI/ML orchestration
- Proof of concept for Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform enabling the mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers
- Proof of concept for Use Case 3: Intelligent connected vehicle with mission-critical services, OTA updates, federated learning/artificial intelligence, and vehicle-to-infrastructure communication.

These key exploitable outcomes will be approached with different exploitation strategies from each partner participating in creation of the current key exploitable result.

The detailed exploitation plan will be based on the intentions of the different partners and will be developed progressively during second half of the project by re-examining at regular times the exploitable results (technical results as well as methodologies and knowledge) of the project. Key exploitable results will be assessed in terms of development status, aspects that facilitate the assessment of the potential impact, differences from existing competing concepts, products or services, etc. The final outcome will be an exploitation roadmap at the end of the project (D6.3).

3.2.1 CONFIDENTIAL TOOLKIT

Confidential toolkit is a set of cryptographic or enablement libraries, SDKs and tools that implement cryptographic primitives, protocols and APIs for confidential computing and confidential networking. These cover Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE), Secure Multi-party Computation (SMPC), Zero-knowledge Proofs (ZKP), DLT and TLS PQC (post-quantum cryptography) and other enablers. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 9.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 9 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Secure toolkit

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
IMDEA: Technological transfer as a result of PhD. Training	The Ph.D. training program will leverage the project results to allow transferring the acquired knowledge to the industry, in sectors such as blockchain and telecommunications. Former Ph. D. students at IMDEA, with expertise in cryptography, are currently employed by companies related to applications of blockchain, such as Protocol Labs, Nomadic Labs and O(1) Labs, and previously by telecommunication companies such as NTT.
NNF: Improvement of NDM DLT confidentiality	NNF's product NDM uses private permissioned blockchain network as a basis of a data exchange platform and leverages on DLT characteristic of transaction immutability to implement secure logging and data monetization. Improved privacy-preserving cryptographic protocols and schemes - notably ZKP and FHE - will help further improve NDM blockchain and enhance the product.
NOK: Enablement of privacy preserving technologies in industrial environments	NOKIA will investigate the state-of-the-art libraries for homomorphic encryption under the prism of industrial applications and relevant algorithms. Based on the conducted analysis NOKIA will obtain a solid understanding of the libraries' capabilities and application domains and define a toolkit that can be exploited for further research and for commercial applications. Attacks against privacy preserving technologies are also considered, in order to understand how the countermeasures of plaintext ML and AI models impact the architecture of FHE designs.
UVC: TEE enablement procedures	UVC will use TEE-handling libraries, cryptographic and other enablers in order to initialize and configure TEE hardware, which is in the base of UVC's product cocos.ai. UVC is working on development of the toolkit

	that includes scripts, executables, and configuration files that will result in a wizard tool that makes process of provisioning process bootstrapping of hardware with TEEs straightforward and unified across different TEE providers.
TID: Distributed, Private, Scalable, Hierarchical FL as a Service	A service (or collection of modules that can be offered as a service) that will enable third-party companies to collaborate and build ML models using the FL paradigm, in a secured, privacy-preserving fashion, using hierarchical and scalable infrastructure of edge and end-user devices, and with a distributed aggregator for scalability and fault tolerance. In 2020-2021, TID filed three patents on the topic of privacy-preserving ML, and in particular, one patent for FL as a Service, one patent for privacy-preserving FL, and a third one on FL with hierarchical DP with hierarchical FL. TID aims to explore further the technologies built within CONFIDENTIAL6G project and how they could be used within on-going services and products of Telefonica.
TNO: Technology transfer to society and industry	TNO has a set of published repositories, the so-called TNO MPC lab, with state-of-the-art Multi-Party Computation building blocks. TNO's MPC lab has many different technologies developed in this toolkit, such as (distributed) homomorphic encryption and MPC by secret sharing. TNO will publish the developed source code for distributed post-quantum fully homomorphic encryption to increase adoption by society and industry. The uptake of solutions will be increased by dissemination activities such as a workshop and a blog and engaging with the cryptography community within and outside of the CONFIDENTIAL6G consortium.
TUE: Technology transfer to students and industry	TUE will use the project's results in its education, training the next generation of engineers and researchers on cutting-edge results for privacy and confidentiality. Prior results from TUE have been widely adopted by industry and included in standards; the key

	to this success is strong results filling a gap, efficient open-source implementations, and wide dissemination to the general developer community. TUE sees the Confidential Toolkit fill a similar need and will contribute its experience to ensuring wide-spread adoption.
VTT: 5G-test network with confidentiality services	VTT's test network laboratory for 5G networks and beyond, which is part of 5G Test Network Finland cooperation, will be enhanced with the trust and security related concepts developed in the project. The laboratory provides an environment to innovate, prototype and test products for future convergent communication infrastructure.
TUG: Technology transfer to students and industry	As a public university TUG will exploit the project's result in training new researchers and engineers in privacy enhancing technologies, such as FHE and MPC. TUG also intends to use the Confidential Toolkit in its effort to research cryptography and publish results at top venues.

3.2.2 CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

Confidential computing is a breakthrough technology that allows to encrypt data in use - while it is being processed. It is often a combination of techniques that leverages on HW-supported TEEs or SW cryptographic enablers like FHE and SMPC. However, these techniques are new, and they build upon cryptographic enablers, a set of more complex components and frameworks, building up the abstraction levels and solution definitions to the very sophisticated applications - like collaborative confidential multi-party AI/ML. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 10.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 10 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Confidential Computing

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
NNF: Edge node AI algorithm protection	NNF will be leveraging TEE-based and enabled edge nodes in order to protect algorithm IPR sent to the node via distributed orchestration. AI/ML algorithms can be of very high value, and often they need to be trained or executed on the data sets that do not belong necessary to a given organisation, and in the edge environments that are not completely in the control of algorithm owners. TEE and FHE-enabled computation nodes will provide sandboxes that will protect algorithms, or/and will enable execution of a code in the encrypted form (algorithm is never shown in the plain text).
NOK: Evaluation of privacy preserving technologies in industrial environments	NOKIA will research industrial use-cases (e.g., predictive maintenance) as evaluation scenarios for FHE technologies and help assess their limitations and practicability as a function of the desired functionality, data size, accuracy of predictions, etc. As such, NOKIA will be in position to evaluate better the technological and business merits of this technology.
UVC: TEE-based secure multi-party computing	UVC's new product cocos.ai uses TEEs to achieve secure multi-party computing. However, there are a lot of challenges regarding security guarantees that the platform provides, and also regarding the implementation of the platform itself. Scheduling of the AI/ML workloads is one example of these challenges, which UVC wants to mitigate using the results obtained in CONFIDENTIAL6G. An open-source software management agent (SMA) that runs within the enclave should be capable to execute this task, while having a minimal code trust base and thus minimal attack vectors. Additionally, this SMA should be capable of fetching and decrypting data sets in

	protected RAM in a reliable manner. Finally, remote attestation handling frameworks should be the outcome of CONFIDENTIAL6G which will be directly used in UVC's platform.
TNO: Technology transfer to society and industry	TNO has a set of published repositories, the so-called TNO MPC lab, with state-of-the-art Multi-Party Computation building blocks. TNO's MPC lab addresses many different technologies for Confidential Computing developed in this toolkit, such as homomorphic encryption and MPC by secret sharing. The results of this project will contribute to the knowledge and implementation repository in the MPC lab and increase the adoption of verifiable computations. In the 3GPP standardisation process it is expected that the 6G studies will be addressed from Release 20 (end 2023) and onwards. This project will contribute to the discussions in the 3GPP SA1 requirements group and the 3GPP SA3 security group. The results of the Confidential Computing can be used in the ISO standardisation process for Multi-Party Computation in which TNO takes part.
WINGS: Federated AI/ML	WINGS will exploit CONFIDENTIAL 6G results on federated AI/ML for confidential computing in the scope of its diverse solutions especially those applied to sensitive domains (e.g. WINGS STARLIT for remote health monitoring, WINGS ARTEMIS for utilities and infrastructures, etc).
IMDEA: Technology transfer	The new results obtained by IMDEA in this project will be published at the main conferences in the area of cryptography and reinforce its strong position in the cryptographic research community. Moreover, IMDEA Software has been assisting local industrial partners in their ongoing development and application of secure multi-party computation platforms for machine learning applications, mainly in the sector of health. The new tools developed in this project, including the collaboration with other partners with different backgrounds, will increase the expertise of the institute in this particular area and its ability to

	transfer their knowledge to industrial applications, which will improve existing collaborations with industry and likely help with establishing new ones.
VTT: Supporting critical application providers	VTT will transfer the developed confidential computing technologies to its customers and partners within society and industry, critical infrastructure, and telecommunication domain. Solutions suitable for different IoT, edge, and cloud platforms will enable our partners to increase security and privacy as well as protect various 6G applications and use cases.

3.2.3 CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING

Confidential networking KER focuses on secure cloud-edge communication and orchestration layer. A very important aspect is further securing TLS and other networking protocols by adding quantum-safe characteristics and ensuring that those implementations are suitable for constrained edge devices as well. Blockchain networking layer will be enhanced in the domain of confidentiality and privacy preservation with ZKPs and FHE-enhanced Smart Contracts, and these SW components will be available for exploitation. Finally, a strong focus is on confidential containers, their support in Kubernetes and Federated AI/ML orchestration - which permits that data stays at the edge and is never moved (rather algorithms are moved towards the data but are protected with encryption and other confidential mechanisms). The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 11.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society.

Table 11 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Confidential Networking

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
NNF: Federated AI/ML orchestration on the top of data marketplace	NNF implemented a secure data exchange platform with distributed access control. Optional monetization feature is based on the underlying blockchain transactions. Top layer exposes Open APIs for programmable operations. Because of those features, this platform is suitable for running more complex

	<p>applications on top, and the customers demanded feature of deploying AI/ML algorithms that can utilise data sets exchanged (or bought and sold) through the platform. For this reason, NNF will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G results in the domain of confidential Federated AI/ML orchestration, which will permit sending algorithms to the edge and applying them there through blockchain-configured distributed proxy data access control, while keeping algorithm IPR protected.</p>
<p>UVC: Confidential containers orchestration</p>	<p>While building platform for collaborative confidential AI/ML, UVC faced the challenge of so called Confidential Containers, a new paradigm that represents adapting of classical Linux containers, Kubernetes CRI and containerization standards like Containers to use Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and their accompanying mechanisms like remote attestations. By exploiting those results from CONFIDENTIAL6G, UVC will completely enable Kubernetes-orchestrated confidential computing, deployed and automated via confidential containers, and this will be a very competitive feature in UVC's cocos.ai platform.</p>
<p>WINGS: Federated AI/ML</p>	<p>WINGS will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G results on federated AI/ML for confidential communication in the scope of its diverse solutions especially those applied to sensitive domains (e.g. WINGS STARLIT for remote health monitoring, WINGS ARTEMIS for utilities and infrastructures, etc).</p>
<p>TUE: Technology transfer via education and to industry</p>	<p>TUE will integrate the results from CONFIDENTIAL6G into its curriculum at the master's and PhD level. Students will be trained on post-quantum cryptography, secure networking protocols, and privacy enhancing technologies such as HFE, MPC, and ZK proofs. TUEs prior research has been standardized by the CFRG and NIST and is available in browsers and operating systems. TUE will leverage this prior success and contacts to ensure widespread adoption of the project's results.</p>

UCD: Technological transfer via Ph.D. training	<p>UCD will perform research and development related to blockchain and federated learning domains. The institute will conduct a well-established and structured Ph.D. training program to transfer the project's results to industrial domains of blockchain and telecommunications. UCD already has a set of Ph.D. courses focusing on cryptography, machine learning, and blockchain. The outcomes of this project will enhance the delivery of these courses while UCD collaboration with the European industries via existing SFI (Science Foundation Ireland) research centres CONNECT (Focus is beyond 5G), Insight (Focus is ML), and ML-Labs (Focus is ML Ph.D. training) will significantly improve through dissemination.</p>
TUG: Technology transfer to students and industry	<p>TUG educates master's and PhD students in the area of cryptography and information security. Thus TUG will include the results of the project into its curriculum, to train a new generation of students on the state-of-the-art in FHE, MPC and ZK-proofs.</p>
FAU: Technology transfer via education and to Industry	<p>FAU will utilise the results in the training program for master's and Ph.D. students in secure multi-party computation, outsourced computation, and cryptocurrencies (in particular in the area of theory and practice of blockchains).</p>

3.2.4 USE CASE 1: PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FOR AIRLINE

Use case 1 is producing application of predictive maintenance in aviation. It demonstrates confidential multi-party AI/ML computation and federated AI/ML orchestration, and verifies techniques produced in WP2, WP3 and WP4, producing practical building blocks for industrial use cases in different verticals. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 12.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers.

Table 12 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use case 1: Predictive maintenance for airline consortium using blockchain-based data sharing platform and federated AI/ML orchestration

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
NNF: Predictive maintenance in aviation use case	NNF created NDM (Nokia Data Marketplace) product for secure data exchange. For the commercial needs, NNF is preparing use cases that are demonstrated to the customers. CONFIDENTIAL6G use case #1 will demonstrate predictive maintenance capabilities but will also enhance features of confidential federated AI/ML orchestration that NNF will reuse in commercial context.
NOK: Predictive maintenance and secure KPI calculation in industrial networks	NOKIA will exploit the learnings from CONFIDENTIAL6G use-case #1, to develop further research Proofs of Concept for advanced predictive maintenance and other AI/ML applications pertaining to industrial applications, like for example secure KPI calculations (from data originating from industrial machinery) and secure SLA maps to optimise factory performance.
WINGS: Predictive maintenance and Digital Twins	WINGS will utilise CONFIDENTIAL6G solutions from this use case to further develop proof of concepts for predictive maintenance combined with federated AI/ML in the scope of Digital Twins for sensitive infrastructure assets.

3.2.5 USE CASE 2: CLOUD PRIVACY-PRESERVING CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING

Use case 2 produces automation procedures of secure VM initialization and configuration in cloud context. These procedures will be usable for many confidential computing applications, as a basic step of HW enablement. It will be especially useful for cloud providers that can offer this feature as a service. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 13.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers.

Table 13 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving confidential computing platform that enables mitigation of internal threats for telecom cloud providers

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
UVC: Automation of TEE initialization and configuration	UVC will exploit CONFIDENTIAL6G use case #2 in two ways: 1) TEE initialization will be directly used in UVC's commercial product as a basis for preparing secure VMs in the cloud environment; 2) Automation of VM-based TEE initialization and configuration, alongside with support for confidential containers will be prototyped into a separate product that can be attractive to various cloud providers and will be marketed in that direction.
VTT: Attestation of telecom cloud services	VTT has developed and trialed telecommunication and trusted computing technologies and concepts for different security critical application domains. In CONFIDENTIAL6G, VTT develops capabilities to take the telecom cloud security into the next level. VTT will be able to help telecom cloud providers to assure and attest trustworthiness of their services and cloud users to deploy their services and data to verified external and cost-efficient cloud platforms. The capabilities will support emerging data federation (GAIA-X) frameworks. The project prototypes, publications, and other references will showcase our capabilities.

3.2.6 USE CASE 3: INTELLIGENT CONNECTED VEHICLE

Connected vehicle use case will deliver an attack resilient communication, and computing environment with vehicles decentralised identities, immutable OEM updates anchored onto the blockchain, and federated learning shared between vehicles and infrastructure. The exploitation strategy is provided for each organisation in Table 14.

Target Group(s): Telecom operators, Service providers, Digital Technology developers, Partnerships, Society

Table 14 Exploitation plan and strategy: KER Proof of concept for Use Case 3: Intelligent connected vehicle, mission-critical services, OTA updates, FL/AI and vehicle to infrastructure communication

Leading partner / Exploitation Asset	Exploitation Strategy
ZEN: Distributed Ledger Technology framework for vehicle identification and OTA updates	<p>ZEN will exploit the knowledge gained in CONFIDENTIAL6G and integrate the resulting components and modules into the company's own solution. Most specifically, DID, DLT and Federated AI/ML will be deployed in the car client, and custom car modules to allow OTA operations with closed-loop systems developed by OEMs. Zentrix partners with onboard car system producer, which will be used as a ground for discussion of the exploitation strategy, to embed produced technology in existing car systems that currently experiments with Blockchain ledger that are less scalable and slower. The service will be deployed and offered to existing clients, as an extended upgraded service with licence including new features, including the device client.</p>
TID: Secure, Private, Scalable, Hierarchical, Collaborative FL Modelling	<p>TID will exploit the results of the third use case in the following ways: 1) TID will assess and investigate issues of secured and privacy-preserving communication and aggregation of models in the FL server in a connected-vehicles setting, as well as other settings that use FL technology for building privacy-preserving ML models. Based on these developments, TID will test ways to protect these settings from FL attacks such as membership inference, attribute inference, data reconstruction attacks, or data poisoning attacks, as well as possible side-channel attacks. 2) TID will use results and data produced from connected vehicles to drive emulations of FL model building when 5G or 6G infrastructure is being used, in order to optimise network connectivity using 5/6G antenna technology and hierarchical and scalable edge computing infrastructure. 3) TID will use the results from this use-case to make decisions on how to perform and tune serverless computing functions and containers to be more secure and privacy-preserving, while facilitating collaborative FL modelling across different third parties on the same local data.</p>
WINGS: Intelligent and	<p>WINGS will leverage results from this use case in potential improvements, in terms of confidential communications, of</p>

secure V2X communication	its WINGSPARK (smart parking solution) and WINGSCHARIOT (secure/safe and trustworthy freight transportation)
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The exploitation of results mostly belongs to the business and commercialization domain which, similarly to science, tends to base its activity on comprehensive analysis, examination of the hypothesis, reaching certainty and achieving planned and expected results. As in science for that purpose, numerous kinds of methodologies, frameworks, tools and models are used, with the basic understanding that there is no perfect model and therefore in order to attain certainty using a multitude of them is the basic principle.

The purpose of the planned Tools and Methodologies for Exploitation of CONFIDENTIAL6G results is exactly to secure maximisation of the commercialization, use and sustainability of CONFIDENTIAL6G results by the scientific, economic, or public stakeholders, transforming R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society. The developed template (Figure 17) will be used within the CONFIDENTIAL6G to track the development status and characterise key exploitable results on the individual (partner) level.

To determine the viability and potential of each exploitable result, we will conduct a detailed market analysis. This analysis takes into account factors such as market size, challenges, available solutions, customer segments, and the economic environment. By gaining valuable insights into customer needs, competition, and regulatory environments, we can make informed decisions on how to exploit our results effectively.

Based on the outcomes of market analysis and feasibility assessment, we make strategic decisions on the best approach to exploit our results. This may involve industrial use, patenting, technology transfer, or publication. We consider factors such as potential partnerships, licensing agreements, and business models to maximise the impact and reach of our innovations.

Active collaboration with European technical initiatives is a priority for us. We engage with and contribute to standardisation technical committees, working groups, and open-source communities of developers. This collaborative approach fosters cooperation, facilitates the seamless integration of our technology into the broader European landscape, and enhances the market potential of our results.

	Organization Name	
	Background IP	
	Current market / existing customers	
Before	Current Exploitation Model	
	Exploitable Result	
During CONFIDENTIAL6G	Description of the Exploitable Result	
	Relation to Objectives	
	Relevant Performance Improvement Targets	
	Relevant WP/Task/Deliverable	
	IPR Protection Method	
	Ownership	
	Type of exploitation	
	Current/Expected TRL	
	Target market(s)	
	Size and growth outlook of target market(s)	
	Target customer segments	
	Competitors	
	Competitive advantages compared to SOTA (state of the art)	
	Key partners	
	Envisaged pricing model	
	Envisaged Sales price and Profit	
	Other useful links/information	

Figure 15 Key exploitable result characterisation template

Within our exploitation strategy, we will develop and update as a part of the deliverables D6.2 and D6.3 a business model that outlines how we plan to generate revenue and sustain the commercial exploitation of our outcomes. The business model encompasses professional-oriented services supported by our core framework, as well as audience-centric services that enable the generation and sharing of new tools and experiences. We favour open-source policies and adopt a dual-licensing approach to manage the knowledge produced internally while also exposing specific knowledge to the scientific community.

While the initial Business Plan is drafted at the proposal stage, a detailed plan is developed and refined within the project activities. This plan outlines the specific steps, activities, and timelines for the commercial exploitation of our outcomes in the medium to long term. It serves as a dynamic observatory and scoreboard, allowing us to monitor and update our progress toward achieving market outreach maturity.

By implementing this detailed exploitation strategy, we aim to transform our project's outcomes into real-world impact. Through careful analysis, intellectual

property management, and strategic decision-making, the full potential of the project exploitation can be achieved.

INNOVATION RADAR

To effectively capture and showcase the project's innovative outcomes, CONFIDENTIAL6G intends to leverage the Innovation Radar platform. Through this strategic utilisation, the project aims to highlight its innovations and gain visibility within the innovation ecosystem. Innovation Radar, a powerful platform for identifying and promoting EU-funded innovations, offers CONFIDENTIAL6G a valuable opportunity to demonstrate its technological advancements and their potential impact.

3.3 INDIVIDUAL EXPLOITATION

In this section of the deliverable the individual exploitation plans are presented. The specific strategies and actions are described to maximise the utilisation and impact of the project's outcomes. Each plan is tailored to address the unique needs and objectives of different stakeholders, partners solution, or its alignment with the organisation mission and development goals. These exploitation plans aim to leverage the transparency and communication capabilities enabled by CONFIDENTIAL6G technologies to drive sustainable practices, enhance trust, and foster collaboration within the industry. By implementing these individual exploitation plans, we can ensure that the project's benefits are effectively harnessed and contribute to long-term positive change in the mining sector.

WINGS develops and delivers solutions (hardware and software) for verticals, related to: a. the Environment, b. Utilities and Infrastructures, c. Production and Manufacturing and d. Service sectors. In the four identified areas, WINGS develops seven (7) products, has launched two (2) spin-out companies and also develops one (1) product that is jointly owned with other companies. All the solutions rely on the following four main pillars: a. Devices. This is centred around IoT (Internet of Things), b. Core platform. This area is centred around 5G and other wireless technologies, edge/cloud, big data platforms, c. Applications. This is powered by AI (Artificial Intelligence) mechanisms. Visualisation, and e. Human in the Loop technologies. WINGS will exploit the outcomes of the project, towards enhancing the company's software solutions so as to extend the supported set of connectivity options and to be able to offer services with enhanced security, privacy and trust. WINGS will pursue valuable synergies with vendors and operators, to set up a

collaborative infrastructure that will enable the delivery of the key exploitable outcomes.

NNF Nokia Networks France (formerly Alcatel-Lucent International) is a trusted partner for critical networks and is committed to innovation and technology leadership across mobile, fixed and cloud networks. NNF's new software solution, called Nokia Data Marketplace (NDM), is a platform for secure data sharing, using innovative technologies like blockchain to assure various aspects of security and data integrity. On the top of this solution, NNF added Federated AI/ML orchestration, aiming to achieve confidential multi-party computations in the future. NNF will leverage on CONFIDENTIAL6G in several aspects: (i) to improve security and confidentiality of the blockchain network behind the NDM product, using ZKPs and FHE for confidential Smart Contracts; (ii) to improve network security using quantum-safe network protocols, like quantum-safe TLS; (iii) to further develop Federated AI/ML features, adding confidential container orchestration with Kubernetes support; (iv) to further enhance and secure access control mechanisms in distributed networks. Finally, NNF will leverage on standards and architectural blueprints created in CONFIDENTIAL6G to align further development and make it interoperable with other security components and other partners and vendors.

NOK Nokia Bell Labs (part of Nokia corporation) for nearly 100 years, has been inventing the future of technology, from the early days of the Bell Telephone System to the latest 5G standards. In the CONFIDENTIAL6G framework, Nokia Bell Labs will benefit in several aspects such as: (i) improve our security capabilities and research footprint on privacy preserving technologies (ii) improve our understanding of the applicability and feasibility of privacy preserving technologies in realistic use-cases of commercial interest for Nokia (iii) prepare for the upcoming changes in the cryptographic domain with the introduction of post-quantum algorithms (iv) enhance our cryptographic agility by gaining solid understanding on the post-quantum TLS design principles and thus help us prepare better our product development lifecycle to accommodate post-quantum TLS.

TID: Telefonica is one of the largest telco providers, operating in 14 countries and serving more than 300 million end-user subscribers, more than 5.5M B2B corporate customers of all sizes. Its latest focus is in 4 principal countries (Spain, Germany, UK and Brazil), in which Telefonica constantly releases new products and services, including AURA (built on the novel data strategy called "4th Platform"), LUCA and Living Apps. Telefonica envisions that through the CONFIDENTIAL6G project, and

its various scalable, privacy-preserving, secured methods, modules and toolkits built within the different components, will be able to improve existing services as well as offer new ones in both B2C and B2B manner, improving compliance with GDPR, Digital Services Act, AI Act, and other related EU and national regulations, as well as go beyond mere compliance by offering even stronger privacy guarantees to all kind of users, from single individuals to large corporate customers involved in complex ML model training. In fact, such ML computation technologies developed within CONFIDENTIAL6G, will be easily applicable to Telefonica's B2B Services such as the Living Apps (which can support internal Telefonica Apps or external 3rd-party services), the Smart Steps service from the LUCA platform, as well as OpenGateway project, the new initiative of Telefonica in coordination with 10s of other telco operators across the world. Also, FL models built with a privacy-preserving fashion could be traded or shared across borders and 3rd-party companies (e.g., other telcos, advertisers, etc.) via the Living Apps and the 4th Platform strategic effort of Telefonica. In particular, Telefonica has more than 300 B2B partners that it collaborates with for different proof of concept technological projects and demonstrations coming out of Telefonica's innovation funnels and other business units. Telefonica's LUCA, with its AI-powered decisions platform, has helped more than 75 companies and other organisations in different sectors such as retail, tourism, utilities, public administration, banking, transport, energy, etc., to deploy successful marketing, business and other corporate strategies. In addition, Telefonica invests a lot in business development, marketing and sales, and participates in the largest industrial events such as Mobile World Congress of GSMA, to promote its new products and services across the globe. The various attack detection and mitigation components can be exploited by the telco's IT and security departments to identify incidents of data leakages and attacks monitoring network traffic and enhancing anomaly detection models and techniques. Finally, being part of such a large telecom operator, TID is especially interested in the novel edge/cloud data services built within CONFIDENTIAL6G, and how they could be applicable in both fixed and mobile environments, transferring results to the Telefonica Tech business unit focused on cybersecurity B2B services. The work done within the project can provide guidelines for edge/cloud network planning, orchestration and design, as well as to understand trade-offs between resource and QoE for CONFIDENTIAL6G.

VTT is a research and technology organisation whose main mission is to provide research and development, technology and innovation services to the Finnish

government and to domestic as well as international companies. The challenges related to cybersecurity, security of 6G and AI are among our research and development target to secure society's functions. The project provides beyond-state-of-the-art results that can be used to facilitate easy adoption of 6G for our industrial and other partners requiring customised security. These results will be passed to domestic and international clients of VTT in order to help them create reliable, robust, and cyber secure 6G solutions and applications. In addition to that, the results will strengthen VTT's expertise related to application of novel platform security technologies towards the next generation of telecommunications and cloud services.

TUE is a public university that is dedicated to excellence in research. This research is expressed through top-quality, publicly available research contributions. In the area of cryptography, the university has strong expertise in the area of post-quantum cryptography and network protocols. This project will further add to this body of expertise and the results of this project will contribute to publications in top venues that will help the university to advance research in the cryptographic research community in a highly visible area. The results will also contribute to the education at TUE, which provides a 2-year master program in cybersecurity with several courses dedicated to cryptography, including post-quantum cryptography and cryptographic protocols, as well as network security. Including cutting-edge results in education helps attract good students and ratings. The project will directly involve the training of a PhD student in cryptography in an area that is immensely important for our digital society. Regarding exploitation of technical results, TUE will not take out patents on any inventions produced during this project and instead will make all research available free and open in order to maximise chance of adoption and standardization. Code produced will be licensed in an open way (public domain or CC0). For previous results, this approach has led to adoption by IETF and NIST as well as major industry players (Apple, Cloudflare, Google, WhatsApp) and inclusion in browsers, thus contributing to better security.

UVC is an SME oriented towards confidential computing and new paradigms of protecting data "in use" and their applications in the telecom, cloud and AI/ML domains. UVC is extensively working on cocos.ai platform, a confidential multi-party computation platform for training and using AI/ML algorithms on combined data sets from mutually distrusting parties. Over the years of development UVC faced a number of still unsolved challenges - specially handling of remote attestations and confidential containers. Their support in Kubernetes is still in the

early phases. UVC plans to exploit these improvements from CONFIDENTIAL6G project, but also to leverage on research that will be executed in the domain of Federated AI/ML. That way the distributed feature can be added to the cocos.ai product. Additionally, optimised FHE and SMPC schemes developed in CONFIDENTIAL6G will be used to replace hardware-dependent component for use-cases where they can present a viable option. TEE abstractions are still immature, and UVC expects to develop a secure Software Management Agent (SMA) throughout the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. This SMA would be capable to accept secure TLS traffic and schedule AI/ML workloads within the secure enclave. Because of this, CONFIDENTIAL6G secure quantum-safe TLS will be used as the feature where opening TLS channels in the secure enclaves (TEEs) is needed. UVC participated at the Confidential Computing Summit in 2023 and presented its work at the EuCNC 6G Summit in 2024 (European Conference on Networks and Communications, supported by the European Commission and the 6G Summit). Here, UVC presented its platform for confidential AI. The confidentiality was supported using AMD SEV-SNP (Secure Encrypted Virtualization-Secure Nested Paging), a hardware technology used to create hardware TEE (Trusted Execution Environments).

ZEN is an SME that operates in different verticals, with commercial solutions for Web 3.0, IoT and DLT. ZEN will exploit the knowledge gained in CONFIDENTIAL6G and integrate the resulting components and modules into the company's existing solution. Most specifically, DID, DLT and Federated AI/ML will be deployed in the Gateway based service for IoT device management and operations. The service will be extended and offered to existing clients, as an upgraded service with licence including new features, as well as next client and markets that we want to target. Additional selling point will be the accommodation and fine-tuning of Zentrix's Blockchain framework with integrated Self-sovereign identity Bridge, Verifiable Credentials, and Audit Stream, which will be enriched with Federated learning capabilities and Anonymous Credentials based on ZKP.

TNO is a non-profit applied research organisation whose mission is to improve and accelerate innovation in society and industry. Specifically in mobile network technology and cryptography, TNO's departments Networks and Applied Cryptography & Quantum Algorithms will contribute in CONFIDENTIAL6G. The department of Networks consists of 60+ people with strong expertise in the field of 5G and 6G, including 3GPP standardisation. The department of Applied Cryptography & Quantum Algorithms consists of 30+ people that are specialised in

SMPC, homomorphic encryption, ZKPs and post-quantum cryptography. TNO has a unique position in the Netherlands to bridge the gap between purely academic research, and the use and development of new technology in real-world applications. TNO's MPC lab is used for publishing and promoting the use of Confidential Computing technologies such as SMPC and (F)HE, with the goal to increase source code quality, improve national and international collaboration and to stimulate adoption. The results of CONFIDENTIAL6G will contribute to standardisation bodies such as ISO (for MPC) and 3GPP (for 6G), as well as publications in top venues that will further strengthen the TNO's position within both the cryptographic and the mobile networking research community.

IMD is a non-profit research institute whose mission is to do academic research of excellence in computer science and more precisely in areas whose goal is to improve the reliability and security of software. In the area of cryptography, the institute has strong expertise in the topics of secure multiparty computation, homomorphic encryption and zero knowledge proofs, among others. The results of this project will contribute to publications in top venues that will further strengthen the institute's position within the cryptographic research community. Moreover, while the main focus of the institute is academic research, it also has frequent collaboration with industry in areas including security and cryptography. This includes recent collaboration with Spanish companies on their development of secure multi-party computation platforms for machine learning applications. The research carried out on this project, as well as the collaboration with the partners, will increase the expertise of the institute in this particular area and its ability to transfer their knowledge to industrial applications, and this will translate into improving existing collaborations with industry and likely establishing new ones. Training of junior researchers will also be an important outcome of the project. Former Ph.D. students and postdoctoral researchers in the institute work currently for telecommunication companies, research labs, especially in the sector of blockchain, and strong academic institutions, which in addition to transferring key technical knowledge to those institutions, provide important research and industrial collaborations for IMDEA. Training as a consequence of this project will reinforce this situation.

TUG: Graz University of Technology (TUG) is the second largest research and education facility for technical sciences in Austria and focuses on high-quality basic research as well as application-oriented research and industrial implementation. The Institute of Applied Information Processing and Communications (IAIK) has

been active in the field of security and privacy for more than 30 years and is one of the leading research institutions in cybersecurity. Cryptographers of the institute have contributed to major worldwide competitions in cryptography (like AES, SHA-3, and CAESAR) and have strong expertise in the area of new quantum-safe cryptosystems (e.g. SPHINCS+ and Picnic) or modern privacy-preserving technologies like homomorphic encryption (e.g. Rasta), secure multiparty computation (e.g. LowMC and MiMC), zero-knowledge proof systems (Poseidon and Starkad), or the first solution for mobile private contact discovery practical for millions of users. This project fits perfectly to the expertise of the institute and will foster its strategic goals as well as strengthen its international standing and visibility. The results of this project will help to advance cryptographic research and contribute to publications in top conferences and journals. Regarding exploitation of technical results within this project, TUG will focus on open-access for all involved publications and developed software (public domain or CC0). The results will also contribute to the education at TUG and the research outcomes will be used to train and educate the next generation of scientists.

UCD: UCD participation in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project will strengthen its research and technical expertise on network security in future networks, Machine Learning and blockchain areas. UCD is also keen to strengthen its ties within the consortium and the relevant technological sectors, fostering future collaborations with top-level academic and industrial partners. As an academic institution, UCD is aiming to enrich its teaching activities at different levels (i.e., Bachelor, Master, PhD, life-long-learning) with respect to network security topics related to future networks, Machine Learning and blockchain areas. This objective will be implemented through two complementary strategies: i) channelling the technological knowledge of CONFIDENTIAL6G to the teaching program and exposing students to real-world problems tackled by the project; ii) incorporating the students in the project and giving them the opportunity to carry out state-of-the art research activities for preparing them to the industrial sectors. Moreover, the project's results will also be used to reinforce the research activities carried out by the university. This will be implemented through: i) incorporating CONFIDENTIAL6G results to the knowledge base of researchers; ii) using the outcomes of the project to strengthen current research initiatives; iii) exploiting the project results as a catalyst for generating further research projects.

FAU: The Friedrich-Alexander-University Erlangen-Nürnberg was founded in 1743, and it is the second-largest university in Bavaria, with almost 40.000 students.

Reuters ranked FAU as the 2nd most innovative university in Europe and 1st in Germany. IT security and cryptography are one of the key areas in the field of computer science. The German Research Foundation supports this area with a dedicated Research Training Group (GTG) in the area of cybercrime, which is an interdisciplinary center between IT Security, Cryptography, and Law. The results of our research are constantly published at the leading venues in IT Security, such as ACM CCS, USENIX Security, and CRYPTO. This project will further sharpen the profile of the CS department and the FAU in general. The results will influence the classes in IT Security and Cryptography in terms of education. Furthermore, all results of this project will be made publicly available, and no patents will be generated.

ABS: Through its participation in the CONFIDENTIAL6G project ABS will enrich its research and technical expertise in the areas of Confidential Computing, Confidential Networking and Cryptography. The research carried out on this project, as well as the collaboration with the partners, will increase the expertise of the ABS and its ability to transfer this knowledge to industrial applications as well as establish further collaborations to foster its growth.

4 IPR KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT

The management of intellectual property rights is a crucial element of strategy that can maximising the value of project innovations. The goal is to establishing clear guidelines for identifying, owning, and granting access rights to the research outcomes. This approach ensures that our intellectual property is adequately protected while promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing within the consortium. We also recognize the importance of timely publication, and the sensitivity of the results that needs to be private before patenting to safeguard European intellectual property rights.

CONFIDENTIAL6G has in place the three key components of an effective IPR system.

1. IP protection framework: We prioritise the establishment of a framework that covers patents, copyrights, branding, and industrial design. This framework will be designed to provide clarity regarding ownership and usage rights, as well as to facilitate the transfer and publication of IP.
2. Technology transfer framework: We we recommend the integration of a technology transfer framework, ideally supported by specialised knowledge transfer offices staffed with experienced professionals, such as the European IPR Helpdesk.
3. Strong legal enforcement framework: Each partner must have a fair and robust legal enforcement system in place to resolve disputes, impose penalties apply appropriate sanctions.

The Consortium Agreement will specifically address and resolve any IP-related issues that may arise. Our main principle regarding IP ownership is that any knowledge generated by a project partner belongs to that partner. In cases where joint development makes it impossible to distinguish individual contributions, joint ownership will be assumed unless the involved parties agree to an alternative arrangement. Concerning background IP, access rights will generally be granted without royalties for project-related activities, unless otherwise specified prior to signing the Grant Agreement.

Aligned with the project's objectives and the partners' interests in industrial exploitation, CONFIDENTIAL6G partners will file patents in areas where they

D6.2 Initial Communication, Dissemination, Standardisation and Exploitation Activities

contribute to advancing the state-of-the-art, particularly in the field of collaborative, privacy-preserving hierarchical federated learning.

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION KPIS AND PROJECT MONITORING

In this chapter, we will present the key performance indicators (KPIs) and project monitoring approach for the dissemination, communication and impact creation activities of CONFIDENTIAL6G. Main focus is to align our dissemination and communication actions with measurable targets and establish an effective monitoring system.

The success of CONFIDENTIAL6G relies on the implementation of dissemination and communication strategies. Therefore, we have identified specific KPIs for each activity to gauge progress and measure the impact of the efforts taken. Monitoring these KPIs will enable to track the effectiveness of dissemination and communication actions and make adjustments if needed.

To facilitate monitoring, partners will have access to an Excel file designed for tracking their dissemination work throughout the project's duration. This comprehensive tracking system will include various parameters, such as press coverage, contributions to specialised journals, presentations at events, and mentions by relevant target groups in public files. By regularly updating the monitoring file, we can assess our performance against the communication KPIs and ensure we are on track to achieve our objectives.

Table 15 provides an overview of the main KPIs for dissemination and communication activities in CONFIDENTIAL6G:

Table 15 CONFIDENTIAL6G Dissemination and communication KPIs

Activity	Performance Indicator	Achieved
Email Campaigns	Contact points (up to the end of the project): ≥ 2000	521
Website	Website online by: M3; Unique Visitors from M36: $> 3,000$	7,780
Social media	Followers (by the end of the project) ≥ 2000 ; No. of impressions (monthly average): > 80	788 followers, 13.877 impressions on LinkedIn and X

Newsletters	Number of newsletters ≥ 10 ;	2
Press Releases	Number of press releases ≥ 6 ;	3
Developer Community	Target Values: Unique Contributions to Developer Communities: ≥ 6	0
Printing / Merchandising	Target Values: No. of hard copies (i.e., brochures, flyers, posters, etc.) distributed ≥ 1500	200 flyers, 200 brochures, 2 posters, 2 rollups. 404 Total
Slide Decks	Target Values: No. of slide decks shared ≥ 6	3
Multimedia Material	Target Values: No. of short videos produced (in total): ≥ 3	0
Logo & Templates	Target Values: Project logo: 1; Templates (deliverables, milestones, presentations, posters) : ≥ 4	1 Logo, 1 ppt template, 1 deliverable template
Project Documentation	Technical publications (including public deliverables: ≥ 10 ; Project brochure: 1 White paper: ≥ 1	7 deliverables, 1 brochure
Peer-reviewed Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific items in journals ≥ 10 ; Peer-reviewed papers in conferences ≥ 10 .	4 Journals, 11 Conference papers
Non-scientific Publications and interviews	Publications in articles, blog posts, position papers, interviews, and any other non-scientific publication oriented end-users ≥ 50 .	30
Coding Guidelines	Coding guidelines paper ≥ 1	0
Source Code Repository	Source code published in ≥ 2 different repositories	1
Open Access	Downloads of CONFIDENTIAL6G material ≥ 1000 ;	478 downloads on

to Research	Online repository: 1; Openly available publications ≥ 15 ; Openly available datasets ≥ 3 ;	Zenodo
Webinars/ Workshops/ Events	Target values: Webinars and workshops ≥ 10 ; Unique participants to webinars and workshops ≥ 200	1
Conferences/ Fairs	Target Values: Fairs to Participate: ≥ 3	0
Working Groups	Target Values: Participation to Working Groups: ≥ 2	2

6 CONCLUSION

This document presents a comprehensive report for the first project interim period of 18 months. CONFIDENTIAL6G has effectively communicated the project's outcomes to various target groups, raising awareness, and inspiring action. The dissemination and communication included a variety of methods to disseminate results, including the CONFIDENTIAL6G website, guidelines, training materials, flyers, brochures, peer-reviewed publications, policy briefs, position statements, non-scientific publications, videos, blogs, webinars, conferences, workshops, newsletters, email campaigns, and open access repositories for research. The plan also highlights the importance of creating focus groups comprising external experts from different target groups to enhance their involvement with the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. The communication strategy includes developing and implementing campaigns to promote the project and its achievements to the target audience, utilising existing networks and ecosystems to facilitate effective communication. The CONFIDENTIAL6G website serves as a central tool for disseminating project information, providing a platform for sharing updates, engaging with target groups, and increasing project visibility. The plan also contains the report and presence on social media platforms like LinkedIn and Twitter for researchers to connect with peers, exchange ideas, and disseminate their work. Additionally, the deliverable addresses the exploitation strategy, which will adapt to the scientific and technological progress and be based on collective and individual exploitation strategies and activities. The Consortium Agreement will define the intellectual property rights (IPR) management strategy, which will significantly influence the exploitation approach. The final version of the exploitation plan will provide a robust strategy for sustaining the partners' outcomes beyond the project's completion. It is important to note that the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plans are dynamic documents that will be continuously updated to align with the project's progress. They will be modified as necessary to enhance and expand the project's outreach to target groups, ensuring effective communication of the CONFIDENTIAL6G vision.